

A MARKETPLACE INVESTIGATION OF CASHEWNUT IN CUDDALORE

Author's Details: A. BALAMURUGAN¹, Dr. S. K.NAGARAJAN²

1. Research Scholar, Dept of Business Administration, Annamalai University, Chidambaram- 002. 2. Guide, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Business Administration, Annamalai University, Chidambaram - 608 002,

Abstract

Cashew is primarily an export-oriented commodity in India. Using a commonly accepted conversion ratio of raw nuts to kernel at 4.54, the volume of processed kernels in the country was worked out. By deducting the quantity of exported kernels from the total processed kernels, domestic consumption of kernels has been derived. The domestic consumption of processed kernels has increased during 2000-01 to 2009-10; the share of kernels exported in the total kernels processed in the country was still 40.84 percent during 2011-12.

Key words: conversion, kernel, consumption

Cashew in India

In India, the Portuguese introduced cashew in the Malabar Coast in the 16th century and the Malabar Coast served as a locus of dispersal to other centres in the country and South East Asia. In the beginning, cashew was mainly considered as a crop for afforestation. As it can adapt to varied agro climatic conditions, it has become a crop of high economy and commercial value. During 2009-10, cashew covered an area of 8.68 lakh hectares in the country with a production of 6.65 lakh MT (DCCD, Cochin).

Objectives of the study

To know the marketing analysis of cashew in Cuddalore district in Tamil Nadu. To know the various marketing problems faced by the respondents. To know the marketing strategies adopted by the farmers. Trends in area, production, yield and price of cashew in the domestic and world market .Production aspects including net income, constraints/ issues in production at farm level. Post harvest management- processing, value addition, methods of processing, bottlenecks faced, etc. Marketing aspects, Credit aspects, Export potential, Strategies for Cashew development.

Review of Literature

Many reviews of related literature especially on consumer behaviour are explored for the purpose of obtaining a thorough knowledge over this field. The materials collected from the reviews expressed by various scholars in the field of consumer behaviour provide a clear background and help to understand the importance of consumer behaviour.

Hypotheses of the study

Respondents do not differ in their methods of various factors in marketing. Farmers do not differ in their problems in cultivation. Respondents do not differ in their level of marketing problems. Farmers do not

differ in their opinion about present marketing system. Respondents do not differ in their credit facilities. Respondents do not differ in their level of satisfaction about price, transport facilities, customer's relationship, on the basis of educational qualifications.

Data used

The data collection pertaining to the study involves only on the basis of primary data and Secondary data. The primary data are collected by means of questionnaire and survey which are used for statistical analysis.

Sample Design

To study the various aspects of marketing of cashew in Cuddalore district, the samples were selected from small, medium and large farmers. Totally 650 samples were selected on the basis of convenient sampling method. Out of 650 samples, 136 samples are selected from large farmers, 256 samples are selected from medium and 258 from small farmers. They were selected from five taluk in Cuddalore district.

Statistical tools used

Statistical tools such as Frequency distribution, One way ANOVA, t-test, Chi-square, Linear Regression model and Correlation are used to analyze the data.

Limitations of the study

The responses from the respondents could be casual in nature. This may be due to lack of interest or time on their part. The correctness of information provided by the respondents in the personal data could not be established. Some of the information provided by the respondents might not be correct. Getting timely responses from the respondents was a difficult task. The reason for this may be attributed to their busy schedules.

Result and discussion

The objectives of the study, hypotheses and methodology were dealt in the previous chapter. In this chapter the researcher has made an attempt to analyse the data related to the present research. The primary data collected from 650 farmers are analysed using certain univariate analyses such as correlation, t-test, mean, standard deviation, chi-square test and ANOVA. The later part of this chapter discusses the application of multivariate analyses such as factor analysis on the collected data.

Member in organization is noted that 46.0 percent of the respondents have membership in organization related to agricultural and very less percent 28.2 in social clubs and 40.8 percent have member in Political participation. So it is concluded that most of the respondents have membership in organization related to agricultural and Political participation.

Problems (Cultivation) farmers expressed that they have problem of getting improved hybrid varieties and 43.7 percent of the respondents says that lack of recommended products practice the crop. Further they also have problem that lack of money and equipment 44.9 percent. Also 39.7 percent of them face problem lack of irrigation water and 48.2 percent of them have shortage of labour, 43.7 percent have lack of sufficient soil testing facilities and 52 percent of them have lack of financing at reasonable interest rates. These are the various problems faced by the farmers at the time of cultivation. This is also statistically proved since the p-value is not significant. So majority of the farmers have problems. So the null hypothesis is accepted. All the farmers face problems.

Market problems are revealed that nearly 66 percent of the respondents have low demand for final products. Also nearly 50 percent of the farmers have receiving low price due high marketing margin. Further 50 percent of the farmers have lack of transportation facilities and road from village to market. Also nearly 40 percent of them expressed that they have lack of regulated market and co-operative markets. Further 43.8 percent of them have lack of even distribution of processing units and nearly 60 percent have lack of storage facilities growing area, nearly 50 percent have lack of awareness about market news and 38 percent have Lack of mechanical grading. This is also statistically proved since the p-value is not significant. So respondents do not differ in their level of market problems.

Opinion about direct market methods It is inferred from the survey that 10.2 percent of them strongly agreed, 22.8 percent of them agreed, 40 percent neither agree nor disagree and 20 percent disagree and 7.1 percent strongly disagree that direct market is more benefited.

Market performances 15 percent of the farmers annual sales up to 5 lakhs , 54.5 percent of the farmers annual sales 5- 10 lakhs and 30.5 percent of the farmers annual sales above 10 lakhs. So majority of them have annual sales 5 to 10 lakhs. In the case of annual income from business 21.5 percent of the farmers up to 2 lakhs , 38.8 percent of the farmers annual income from business 2-5 lakhs and 39.7 percent of the farmers annual income from business above 5 lakhs.

Regarding mode of sales 53.38 percent of the respondents preferred only cash sales and remaining have credit sales. In the case of deliver method counter sales 33.7 percent of them preferred. 22.6 percent preferred door delivery. 23.8 percent preferred mail order supply. Regarding Sales Promotion methods 29.2 percent discount and 39.4 percent contests. Trend line of farmer's total profitability trending up 44.3 percent and trending down 42.5 percent. Here based on the statistical result the null hypothesis is accepted.

Credit period allowed for suppliers, no credit period allowed 19.7 percent, Less than 15 days 21.5 percent, 15 days to 30 days 34.8 percent and more than 30 days 24.0 percent. In the case of credit period allowed to customers no credit period allowed 28.5 percent, Less than 15 days 25.4 percent, 15 days to 30 days 27.5 percent and more than 30 days 18.6 percent. Here the statistical result proves that the null hypothesis is accepted. $P >= 0.05$.

It is inferred from the above table that the obtained F-value for respondents opinion regarding price is significant. But they do not differ in their opinion about transport and CRM. $P > 0.05$. So the stated null hypothesis only for price it is not accepted and for the remaining factors it is accepted. About the price of the product degree qualified respondents are differ in their opinion.

Showing Anova for respondents level of satisfaction about price, transport facilities, customers relationship, product price, place immediately, Improving my marketing, present marketing on the basis of land:

The above table showing Anova for respondents level of satisfaction about grading, transport facilities, customers relationship, product price, advertisement, marketing facilities and present marketing on the basis of land. It is inferred from the above statistical result that respondents do not differ in their opinion about grading system and transport. But in other factors they differ in their opinion. Since the calculated F-values are significant. Therefore it is concluded that respondents differ in their level of satisfaction about customers relationship, product price,

advertisement, marketing facilities, present marketing on the basis of land.

Finding

About the price of the product degree qualified respondents are differ in their opinion. It is concluded that respondents differ in their level of satisfaction about customers relationship, product price, advertisement, marketing facilities, present marketing on the basis of land. It is inferred from the statistical result that regarding technology facilities and payment system farmers differ in their level of satisfaction. But in other factors such as selling with value addition and financial assistance they do not differ in their opinion. It is inferred that only in Marketing facilities, Market price, hybrid varieties and crop they differ in their opinion. But in other factors they do not differ in their level of satisfaction. Female respondents are not satisfied about marketing facilities, market price, hybrid varieties and crop. There is an association between type of farmer and mode of marketing the procedure. It is concluded that there is an association between type of farmer and whether the seller approaching you. There is an association between type of farmer and how you know the product price. It is concluded that there is an association between type of farmer and selling from.

Conclusion

The study makes an attempt to know the marketing analysis of cashew in Cuddalore district - Tamilnadu among the farmers. The study concluded that irrespective of land size the farmers are not get sufficient support from the government for their marketing. They also lacking in labour facilities and transport facilities. Further they are lacking in information channels to get more awareness about the market. Therefore the research

suggested that the government and related agricultural departments take steps to do all the necessary helps to promote the farmers in all aspects.

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